

IN EFFECTIVE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM SCIENTIFIC ANALYSIS OF
MAIN POSSIBILITIES AND THEORETICAL INTERPRETATION

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to promising areas of tourism development. It has been analyzed economic condition of tourism development in Uzbekistan. Besides, it has been given scientific recommendations for solving important issues in tourism.

Keywords: tourism industry, regional development, foreign tourists arrivals, tourist services export.

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Abstract: Данная статья посвящена перспективным направлениям развития туризма. Проанализировано экономическое состояние развития туризма в Узбекистане. Кроме того, были даны научные рекомендации для решения актуальных проблем в сфере туризма..

Keywords: туристическая индустрия, региональное развитие, визит иностранных туристов, экспорт туристических услуг

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Abstract: Мазкур мақола туризм соҳасини самарали ривожлантиришнинг устувор йўналишларига бағишланган. Ўзбекистонда туризм соҳасини ривожлантиришнинг иқтисодий ҳолати ҳам таҳлил қилинган. Бундан ташқари, туризм соҳасидаги долзарб муаммолар ечимига бағишланган илмий таъсиялар келтириб ўтилган.

Keywords: туризм индустрияси, минтақавий ривожланиш, хорижий туристлар таширифи, туристик хизматлар экспорти.

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Enter

At a time when globalization processes are deepening on a global scale tourism has become an important source of income for the economy of many countries managed to The tourism industry is a driving force for creating new jobs acquires social importance as "Today, the world's gross domestic product is about 10% of production, 9% of employment, 7% of total exports percent, and 30 percent of the export of services is accounted for by the tourism sector".

This confirms its important place in economic development. According to the analysis, every year 148 million tourists around the world make pilgrimages travels for the purpose of The situation related to the pandemic is again this year if it does not become complicated, the number of pilgrims coming to Samarkand will increase to 210,000 delivery is available.

World exports include tourist services, fuel, chemical industry, and food and the fact that it ranks fifth after the export of the automobile industry significant impact on the development of economic sectors indicates that it is showing.

Foreign countries have their own national tourism export volume of tourist services based on product diversification began to pay serious attention to regular improvement. In particular, in Uzbekistan activities of business entities engaged in inbound tourism modernization, tourist services based on innovative technologies improvement of the state policy to diversify its exports great attention is paid as one of the priority directions.

Analysis of literature on the topic

The methodological foundations of the development of the tourism industry are foreign and studied as an important research subject in the scientific work of local scientists. In particular, the scientific one devoted to the development of the tourism industry one of the most important sources is to list the research works of V. I. Azar possible.

Also scientific works of local scientists published in recent years noteworthy. The trends in the development of tourism and recreation services were analyzed in scientific works published by Z.I.Usmonova.

J.N. Abiev to develop the tourism network in the national economy studied economic aspects. Historical and cultural by Sh.R.Ruziev organizational and economic mechanism of tourism development and its improvement issues have been studied. Methodology of ecological tourism management by O.H.Hamidov the issue of improving the basics has been thoroughly studied. A.K.Alimov environmentalist in the matter of priority directions and prospects of tourism development conducted monographic studies. Tourism by A.A. Eshtaev development of a marketing strategy for the industry and its management methodology has been studied.

However, the field of tourism in the scientific and practical research carried out to date. There are enough problems to determine the priorities of effective development not studied to the extent. This research work deals with the same aspects of the issue covered.

Research methodology

During the research work, observation, comparison, systematic and comparative analysis, methods such as statistical grouping and expert evaluation were used. Specifically, from ten in-depth interviews with respondents at more tourist sites was established. As a result, the gender, age, information on demographic indicators such as education, income collected. In addition, between managers of tourist activities.

Analytical research was conducted based on the focus group method. Studies as a result, the composition of the main tourist products offered to tourists was studied. The main scientific results obtained during the research work. State Statistics of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to ensure its reliability Committee information was used.

Analysis and results

The state also attaches great importance to the development of the tourism industry and service provision in Uzbekistan. PF-5326 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 3, 2018 "Favorable conditions for the development of the tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan

"On additional organizational measures to create" and directions for comprehensive use of existing resources and opportunities of historical heritage are strictly defined.

In many countries with a highly developed tourism industry, favorable conditions have been created for foreign tourists to relax and provide them with quality services, which steadily attract millions of tourists. At the same time, it should be noted that the share of regions such as Africa, Australia, South America, Southeast Asia, and Mexico in providing services to foreign tourists is increasing.

Today, the growth of the national economy depends on the world market.

Tourism not only brings countries closer to each other, but also becomes an important factor in the development of international relations. Therefore, there is a need to rationally organize, manage and develop the international tourism industry, increase and improve the types of accommodation facilities, and apply world experience in this regard.

The results of the economic, social and institutional reforms carried out in the country are reflected in the changes taking place in the country and the growth of statistical indicators of industry sectors. The results of reforms in the field of tourism in our country are also reflected in changes in economic indicators in this field. Every made economic and institutional changes should be implemented effectively and reflect successful results while aiming at the development of the country.

The evolution of institutional changes in the field of tourism has given rise to major changes. The number of tourists coming to Uzbekistan has increased by 3-4 times in a short period of time, excluding the pandemic period. This is a great indicator in the development of world tourism. 7 million in 2019. The number of tourists shows that the tourism reforms are effective and on the right track.

The beginning of reforms in the field of tourism, in turn, requires the representatives of the sector to carry out a comprehensive and structural analysis of the changes in the sector.

In one such analysis conducted by the Ministry of Tourism and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the composition of tourists who came to our country was studied separately.

The results showed the purpose of the tourists coming, and through this indicator, it was reflected which types of tourism in the country should be expanded and developed in the future. Visits according to the classification of goals and their general status are reflected in the table below.

Distribution of tourists to Uzbekistan by purpose

No	Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021
	Total: for the following purposes:	2 027 035	2 690 074	5 346 219	6 748 512
1	Relaxation and entertainment (15,5%)	175 534	230 513	458 119	1 043 929
2	Trade (0,8%)	17 175	25 635	50 946	53 874
3	Business meetings (0,8%)	149 708	28 437	56 515	53 117
4	Treatment and recovery (0,8%)	27 149	26 430	52 527	55 490
5	Education (0,3%)	6 261	7 363	14 633	21 383
6	Seeing relatives and friends (81,8%)	1 651 208	2 371 696	4 713 479	5 520 719

According to Table 1, the majority of tourists who come to the country are to visit relatives and friends, which requires more attention to be paid to the development of the rest of the tourism destinations in our country and the conclusion of improving the infrastructure of the most visited tourist destinations.

Major changes and reforms in the field of tourism, in turn, are important with an increase in the demand for personnel. Reforms in this regard are also being carried out in our country. Currently, there are a total of 6,738 courses in the field of tourism in 25 higher educational institutions of the republic. A student is studying.

In the 2020-2021 academic year, 3340 students were admitted to 10 colleges and 3 technical schools, which were transferred to the Ministry of Tourism and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan, on the basis of a state grant. The building of the "Silk Road" International University of Tourism in Samarkand was completely renovated, and on October 16, 2020, the opening ceremony of the renovated building of the university was held. Education at the International University of Tourism "Silk Road" was launched entirely in English.

In this university, Guilin Tourism University of China (Guilin Tourism University, China) in the field of "Management: hotel management", Sahid Polytechnic Institute of Indonesia (Sahid Polytechnic in Jakarta) in the fields of "Management: Tourism Business Management" and "Public Event Management" Staff training was launched on the basis of joint educational programs with the Sahid Tourism Institute (Sahid Institute of Tourism in Surakarta) in the field of "Management: Restaurant Business Management".

International scientific tourism journal "Uzbekistan Travel" has been published. In order to increase the scientific potential in the field of tourism, the admission processes for doctoral studies and basic doctoral studies were carried out at the Institute of Tourism Development and the "Silk Road" International University of Tourism. At the heart of any economic reforms is the role of education and the personnel training system.

In particular, the processes of training personnel for the tourism sector are being implemented as an integral part of the economic reforms being carried out in the country. As mentioned above, currently 25 higher education institutions are preparing personnel for the field of tourism at the bachelor's and master's levels. The results of the analysis of these cases show that (Fig. 2), 187 professors and teachers are currently working in higher education institutions that train personnel for the tourism industry. Of these, 11 (6 percent) are doctors of science, 13 (7 percent) are PhDs, and 33 are candidates of science. 22 of them are professors and teachers who graduated from foreign higher education institutions and 57 (30.5 percent) are professors and teachers with academic degrees. At the same time, 15 of them (8 percent) are professors and teachers who have a scientific degree in the field.

Conclusions and suggestions

In order to diversify tourism products and services aimed at different segments of the tourism market, it is advisable to implement the following:

- launch of additional infrastructure facilities based on the most advanced and innovative technologies in the framework of the development of extreme and mountain tourism in the Tashkent region;

- for audiovisual products obtained in the republic for the purpose of developing film tourism

- simplification of the procedure for reimbursing part of the expenses of foreign film companies;

- based on the nature and traditions of neighborhoods and villages, expanding the organization of "Tourism neighborhood", "Tourism village" and "Tourism village" in order to increase tourist attractiveness and ensure the flow of tourists;

- in order to create conditions for the development of types of tourism, it is necessary to accelerate the establishment of the tourism transport corridor "Uzbekistan tourism highway" along the highways. In general, the evolution of institutional changes in the field of tourism in our country consisted of several stages. As a product of gradual development, the tourism sector has its own rich history and huge resource potential. In conclusion, it is necessary to activate the practical efforts in this field by determining the priority directions based on the scientific analysis of the main opportunities in the development of the tourism sector.

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